

Validation for Different Testing Techniques used for Turbine Control System and Turbine Protection System used in a Supercritical Thermal Power Plant

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Abstract

This paper addresses the techniques to ensure the safety and quality of the distributed control system. This system is dedicated for turbine's controlling and protection in a thermal power plant. Prior to delivery or final installation, customer wants an assurance that equipment operates as intended without disturbances occurring onsite. For this assurance the set of test performed sequentially so that the manufacturer and client can verify that all the specifications and contractual requirements have been fulfilled. These test techniques are for performance of analog and digital signals for the processing period of the controllers and nature of system in various conditions.

Keywords

Turbine; Control system

Introduction

The thermal power plant is a giant process in which several processes and applications are involved. Therefore, to monitor and control every specific application, a control configuration system is designed, which is distributed control system. This configuration is further divided into subsystems dedicated for a specific application. Here, let's explore the controlling and protection of the most important component of the plant, i.e. turbine. Turbine control system incorporates control function, i.e. speed control, governor/load limit control, valve transfer, turbine stress calculation, valve testing, valve management, which is implemented by software and hardwired logic. Likewise, turbine protection system is also a separate system with certain protection control configuration.

Background

This TCS/TPS system works on redundant CPUs. The complete controlling is being done with the CPU and the dedicated cards for different functions like Ethernet, I/O modules, CPU cards, etc. The logics in the control panel are provided through flashcard.

This system has multiple panels. In TCS, first panel is the control panel which is controlling the rest of the panels. Control panel has the complete CPU chassis arrangement, with power supply and cards, whereas, different communication modules like Ethernet, control net and D-ring, I/O network. Other than first two panels, all the panels are completely designed with I/O modules in front and relays and terminal blocks at the rear side. Similarly, in TPS, there are three control panels.

Figure 1: Control System Configuration

Factory Acceptance Test

After the wide literature research, the thermal control technology institute of Guang Dong Electric Power Research Institute has given a complete set of techniques for site performance test. The testing includes power supply, HMI, inspection of I/O signals, maintainability, anti-jamming tests, etc. Let's discuss the testing techniques for TCS/TPS performed in industries.

High Voltage Test:

In this test, when the design of the panels with basic components mounted in it is done, like dinrails, Terminal Blocks, relays, power supply, etc. then these panels are supplied with 1-1.5 kHz for a short time, and then the tolerance of the panel is inspected in high voltage conditions. In this test, the major I/O modules, cards, CPU, etc. are not involved because they are sensitive to HV.

BOM Test:

BOM is Bill of Material. It is a list of batch or components that are required to build a

product. It provides part no. and quantity of components to the manufacturer. And accordingly, all the components inside the panel are tested.

Continuity Test:

It is the testing of the electric circuit to see if current flows. This test is performed by placing a small voltage across the chosen path. If electron flow is inhibited by broken conductors, damaged components or excessive resistance, the circuit is opened. We use multimeters or a buzzer circuit to test the path. If the path is short circuited, we will get a B and if not, the fault is occurred.

Power Test across the components:

For the TCS/TPS panels, the components work on 24 V DC. Through the loop handy calibrator, we will test the voltage across the components and set the value with the tolerance limit of 0.2 or 0.7 volts, according to component.

Figure 2: loop handy calibrator diagram

RAS (Reliability, Accessibility, and Serviceability) Test:

This test is basically for quality inspection of the panels once all the modules have been placed. For this test, an oscilloscope is connected and two PCs which monitor the logics and operation of the system through dedicated software. In oscilloscope, three signals are displayed. One of them is for system, a triangular wave for analog signals and a square wave for digital signals. According to the predefined procedure, one by one, modules are taken off and then the nature of the system is observed whether the system stays healthy or fails. According to the behaviour, the observations are noted down. The nature of the system will also affect the signals displayed in oscilloscope. If the system is healthy, the wave forms stay same, and if not, then all the signals turn into a straight line. Likewise, we test the reliability, serviceability and accessibility of the system.

Figure 3: RAS test set-up

Environmental and Hammer Test:

This test is done for the sustainability of the system in all the environmental conditions. In this test, the mobile signals are interfered with the input signals given to the system. This experiment should not affect the working of the system or processing of the signals. Whereas, in hammer test, the modules mentioned in the procedure, are banged through the hammer and then the response of the system as well as the modules working is observed, if it stays healthy or stops working.

Simulation Test:

During this test, we are checking the turbine tripping conditions. A virtual environment of field signals is provided with all the type of signals for controlling a turbine. A set of procedures is given to be followed for test, accordingly, the switch in the simulator is selected and the turbine conditions are observed in dedicated computer system. If the nature of the turbine is according to the predefined results, then the test is successful, or else, the logics are needed to be checked.

Figure 4: Testing Drives

Conclusion

Testing in industries is the key requirement for all the manufacturing goods for its customer acceptance. Likewise above mentioned are the basic testing technique followed for the DCS in thermal power plant. It is most reliable way to test the controllers with all the future conditions good or bad and sufficient for customer's satisfaction.

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